

14 April 2025

Press release

On 10 March 2025, the CST4ALL project hosted the online “Industry Workshop on the hybridisation of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with geothermal”, organised by ESTELA with contributions from all project partners and the support of the European Technology & Innovation Platform on Geothermal (ETIP-Geothermal). The workshop brought together 100 stakeholders from the energy sector across 20 countries worldwide, including representatives from the European Commission (EC), national authorities, industry, associations, engineering and consultancy firms, research institutions and universities, to explore the industrial potential of integrating CST and geothermal technologies.

Dr. Konstantinos Genikomsakis of ESTELA opened the event by introducing the CST4ALL project’s activities and workshop’s objectives, followed by Dr. Hande Eryilmaz of ODTÜ-GÜNAM who presented the ongoing public opinion survey on Green Deal challenges & social sciences and humanities and gender aspects within the project.

On behalf of the EC, Elisabeth Schellmann outlined the EU's current energy policy priorities, focused on balancing ambitious decarbonisation goals with industrial competitiveness. The Clean Industrial Deal aims to make Europe attractive for both energy-intensive industries and clean technologies, while promoting circularity and addressing high energy costs. The Affordable Energy Action Plan, a key part of the Clean Industrial Deal, aims to lower energy costs, complete the Energy Union, attract investments and ensure research innovations are deployed within Europe, and enhance readiness for future energy crises. Upcoming funding of €600 million will be allocated to deployment-ready clean tech projects, while the forthcoming Industrial Decarbonisation Accelerator Act will further support energy-intensive industries, building on the existing Net-Zero Industry Act that already includes CST and geothermal technologies.

The keynote presentations addressed the opportunities and challenges of CST-geothermal integration. Diego Caro Pegalajar of ACCIONA Industrial presented design and operational issues of CSP plants and discussed hybridisation possibilities with geothermal technologies, identifying key limitations and main drivers for improving electricity production and grid stability. Dr. Konstantinos Genikomsakis presented on behalf of Dario Bonciani from the Consortium for the Development of Geothermal Areas (COSVIG), focusing on the technological advantages of hybrid CST-geothermal systems for power production compared to standalone systems, along with the challenges that need to be addressed. Dr. Ahmet Lokurlu of Soliterm Group GmbH showcased a range of possible CST applications including electricity and hydrogen production, desalination, steam generation for industry, district heating and cooling, along with a small-scale hybrid CST-geothermal system in Bochum, Germany, with plans for larger-scale use for seasonal heating and cooling.

During a live poll, participants identified securing robust project financing and mitigating investment risks as the most critical factor for enabling large-scale adoption of hybrid CST-geothermal systems in

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Europe, followed by the need to advance technological readiness and overcome key technical challenges, and identify the most viable applications for hybrid CST-geothermal systems.

The roundtable discussion, moderated by Dr. Rosie Christodoulaki of the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRESES), featured a diverse panel of experts from both sectors to exchange views on the importance of addressing challenges related to technological readiness, project financing, application viability, skills and workforce development, policy frameworks, research and innovation, market potential and collaboration between the two sectors.

In the wrap-up session, Dr. Peter Heller, coordinator of the CST4ALL project, summarised the workshop's key insights. A key takeaway was the strong consensus that hybrid CST-geothermal systems hold significant potential to improve energy security, grid stability, and decarbonisation across various applications beyond electricity production, such as industrial process heat and district heating and cooling. However, the panel of experts underlined the need to explore the viability of these hybrid systems in different locations and conditions, implement pilot demonstrations to build investor and stakeholder confidence, establish supportive policy frameworks with long-term incentives, as well as foster cross-sector collaboration to integrate knowledge and comprehensive resource data from both energy sectors, and importantly, develop strategic approaches tailored to industrial needs and regional advantages to advance hybrid CST-geothermal systems.

ETIP Geothermal

This CST4ALL project event was organised with the support of the European Technology & Innovation Platform on Geothermal (ETIP-Geothermal).

CST4ALL Coordinator

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German Aerospace Center

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CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT
Centro de Investigaciones
Energéticas, Medioambientales
y Tecnológicas

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (ES)

ITALIAN NATIONAL AGENCY FOR NEW TECHNOLOGIES,
ENERGY AND SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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The CST4ALL project is committed to catalysing an array of hybridisation and cooperation initiatives at the interface between CST and other renewable energy technologies targeting the electricity, heat, and fuels sectors.

To stay up-to-date on CST4ALL's activities and opportunities, follow the project on:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cst4all/>
- X (formerly Twitter): <https://twitter.com/Cst4All>
- Website: <https://cst4all.eu/en/>

You can also sign-up for the **CST4ALL Newsletter** to receive updates on other project events and outputs through the following link: <https://cst4all.eu/en/4169-contact-connect>.

